

DEEP LEARNING SEGMENTATION OF THE PORCINE SUPERFICIAL FEMORAL ARTERIES OCT IMAGES

Miloš Anić^{1*}, Sotiris Nikopoulos², Siaravas Konstantinos², Christos S. Katsouras^{2,3},
Vasiliki Potsika¹, Nenad Filipović^{4,5}, Dimitrios Fotiadis^{1,6}

¹Unit of Medical Technology and Intelligent Information System, University of Ioannina, Ioannina, Greece

e-mail: anic.milos@kg.ac.rs

²Dept. of Cardiology, Medical School, University of Ioannina, Ioannina, Greece

³Michaelidion Cardiac Center, University of Ioannina, Ioannina, Greece

⁴University of Kragujevac, Kragujevac, Serbia

⁵BioIRC – Bioengineering Research & Development Center, University of Kragujevac, Kragujevac, Serbia

⁶Biomedical Research Institute, FORTH, Ioannina, Greece

**corresponding author*

Abstract:

Peripheral artery disease is an atherosclerotic disease that represents accumulation of cholesterol in any artery, excluding coronary arteries, while forming different types of depositions called plaques, which cause thickening of the arterial walls which makes it difficult for the blood to flow to lower extremities. According to the statistics, approximately 8.5 million Americans aged over 40 years are affected by peripheral artery disease, out of which one fourth falls into the severe category. For these reasons, it is extremely important to detect the disease as soon as possible. In this paper we provide a deep learning approach for lumen and intima segmentation of porcine femoral arteries as an important pre-step for the use in humans. Method proposed in this paper focuses tree different convolutional neural networks and highlights the difference in results. Proposed networks include modified U-Net, SegNet and PSPNet networks. Modifications include the use of different encoders in the case of SegNet and PSPNet and modification from the aspect of depth for U-Net architecture. We evaluated our methods on manually annotated OCT images from 8 specimens in terms of F1-score and overall quality of the reproduced masks. Experimental results show that modified U-Net provides us with the best results for lumen and intima segmentation with F1-scores 0.9842 and 0.9672. Results also show that modified U-Net outperformed other architectures proposed in the literature.

Keywords: convolutional neural networks, segmentation, peripheral artery, optical coherence tomography, deep learning